

Study of the Effect of Radiation Dose on the Kinetics of Annealing of Barium Nitrate

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Chemical annealing of the damage nitrite in irradiated alkali metal and alkaline earth metal nitrates in their solid state has been studied extensively¹. The effect of high doses of radiation on the kinetics of high temperature annealing has not received much attention. The present investigation relates to annealing of nitrite in pure crystals of barium nitrate irradiated to 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 MGy of Co-60 gamma-ray followed by isothermal annealing in temperature range 673—753 K for 30 h.

Results and Discussion

Barium nitrate crystals develop a faint yellow colour upon exposure to gamma-irradiation which disappears on heating the sample within 10 h. The amount of nitrite in barium nitrate produced by

absorption of 1.0, 2.0 and 4.0 MGy was found to be 13200, 13625 and 14336 g/10⁶ g respectively. Kinetics of isothermal annealing of nitrite were studied in the temperature range 673—753 K for different time intervals up to 30 h. It was observed that the recovery of nitrite is rapid initially but slows down at later stage². The fraction annealed ϕ value at different annealing temperature also increases with increase in radiation dose and temperature of heating (Fig. 1).

The annealing data have been analysed on the models for simple interstitial vacancy recombination and also on the basis of diffusion-controlled reactions. The application of the Fletcher-Brown treatment³ for the annealing data shows that the reaction is a combination of first and second order

Fig. 1. Dependence of fraction annealed, ϕ vs t at 673 and 753 K with different radiation doses : (1) 1.0, (2) 2.0, (3) 4.0 MGy at 673 K ; and (4) 1.0, (5) 2.0, (6) 4.0 MGy at 753 K.

Fig. 2. Fletcher-Brown composite annealing curve at different doses of irradiated barium nitrate: (O) 673, (Δ) 693, (\square) 713, (\bullet) 733 and (\blacktriangle) 753.

processes (Fig. 2), which fit the general equation of the type,

$$\phi = x \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t'}{A}\right) \right] + y \left[\frac{1}{1 + B/t'} \right]$$

where t' is the equivalent annealing time at reference temperature (713 K), x and y are the first and second order contributions to the annealing process, A and B are constants evaluated by computer calculations from the annealing data at various temperatures. The energies of activation calculated from Fletcher-Brown model (E_{FB}) of first and second order processes (E_{1st} and E_{2nd}) are recorded in Table 1. With increase in radiation dose the 1st order contribution increases, but the 2nd order contribution decreases, which indicates that radiation dose increases the rate of diffusion of damage fragments.

TABLE I

Dose MGy	X	Y	A	B	E_{FB}	E_{1st}	E_{2nd}
1.0	0.042	0.958	1.201	368	135.942	48.594	100.422
2.0	0.049	0.951	1.305	377	125.510	37.250	88.382
4.0	0.061	0.939	1.348	385	112.929	23.616	90.050

The Waite model⁴ suggests that the annealing process is a single diffusion-controlled bimolecular reaction. By considering the Smoluchowski boundary condition⁵ (SBC) and Radiation boundary condition⁶ (RBC), it is evaluated that annealing is a function of parameter Z ,

$$Z = \frac{2(Dt)^{1/2}}{r_0} \quad (1)$$

where, Z is the reduced diffusion length, a dimensionless quantity, D the sum of diffusion coefficients of the reacting species and r_0 the capture radius. The annealing data of barium nitrate has been analysed by applying Waite model, where ϕ is proportional to Z for initial period indicating the combination of close correlated pairs in accordance with SBC approach. Increase in radiation doses decreases the initial linear period suggesting the decrease in the concentration of species inside the capture radius. On prolonged annealing, linearity of the plot ϕ vs Z (Fig. 3) differs due to the recombination of un-correlated species available outside the capture radius.

Fig. 3. Linearity in Waite model for barium nitrate irradiated to different doses as a function of Z : (O) 673, (Δ) 693, (\square) 713, (\bullet) 733 and (\blacktriangle) 753 K.

All the samples of $Ba(NO_3)_2$ follow the similar pattern of initial first order and then a second order processes. Most of the fragments generated in various fast reactions are ultimately converted by NO_2^- and O or NO and O_2^- species. These species combine by a first order and second order mechanism. During initial period, there is combination of close correlated pairs where the concentration of $O_2^- \gg NO$ or $NO_2^- \gg O$, hence the rate is pseudounimolecular. In the latter stage both the concentrations affect the rate, hence it is second order. It is concluded that the recovery of damage fragments increases with increase in radiation dose and temperature.